

INTEGRATION OF THE FINANCIAL LITERACY INTO THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS IN TERMS OF SDGS

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Annotation. *In the modern world aimed at achieving SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals), the question of how to properly manage your finances has arisen. In this regard, various programs have begun to emerge in the system of secondary and higher education to increase the financial literacy of the population. This article examines the concept of «financial literacy» and the process of improving financial literacy education in the country's scope.*

Key words: *financial literacy, economic education, state, financial skills.*

Аннотацыя. *В современном мире, направленном на достижение ЦУР, возникает вопрос о том, как правильно управлять своими финансами. В связи с этим, в системе среднего и высшего образования начали появляться различные программы, направленные на повышение финансовой грамотности населения. В данной статье рассматривается понятие "финансовая грамотность" и процесс повышения финансовой грамотности населения в масштабах страны через образование.*

Ключевые слова: *финансовая грамотность, экономическое образование, государство, финансовые навыки.*

Annotatsiya. *SDG (barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlari) ga erishishga qaratilgan zamonaviy dunyoda moliyangizni qanday qilib to'g'ri boshqarish kerakligi haqida savol tug'ildi. Shu munosabat bilan o'rta va oliy ta'lim tizimida aholining moliyaviy savodxonligini oshirish bo'yicha turli dasturlar paydo bo'la boshladi. Ushbu maqolada "moliyaviy savodxonlik" tushunchasi va mamlakat miqyosida moliyaviy savodxonlik bo'yicha ta'limni takomillashtirish jarayoni ko'rib chiqilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *moliyaviy savodxonlik, iqtisodiy ta'lim, davlat, moliyaviy ko'nikmalar.*

The overall global context is reflected through not only through environmental conventions, social initiatives or health literacy, but also touches upon labour relations and financial competence. The hierarchical priorities of the Republic of Belarus regarding an inclusive and sustainable education have modeled the present-day educational curriculum with acceleration of SGGs (Sustainable Development Goals) promotion at all levels. It has put in place a long-term reform to improve the quality of public finance management skills. The term financial literacy is the ability to understand money and make sound financial decisions. Understanding the language of money, knowing how to build and maintain good credit, and managing money by preparing a family budget are all a part of being financially literate. It is essential to become financially literate to maintain good financial health. A financially literate person would be unable to make better financial decisions that would improve his or her social and personal financial well-being.

Financial literacy is not only the understanding of monetary transactions, but also the shaping of personal views and assessments of the roles and purposes of these transactions. As

one of the fundamental factors in ensuring the sustainable development of humans not only as economic agents, but also as free individuals, it is clear that this is a key factor in the economic growth and macroeconomic stability of countries [1].

Financial education is often called one of the functions of the state. Nevertheless, the experience of developed and developing countries shows that financial behavior is formed under the influence of many other entities and institutions, including the functioning of the education system and the social sphere, the institutional framework of the financial services market, and the level of trust in these institutions.

It is believed that no nation can grow and prosper to its full potential without a financially literate population. A financially literate society would induce economic growth and faster development in the country, enable better individual financial well-being, and establish financial stability due to the applicable use of financial products. It has been figured out that the level of financial literacy is an important factor that explains how and why people save, invest, and adopt social and economic financial products. It is important at the country level because it could influence a wide range of social and economic outcomes, such as long-term growth, health, education as well as individual wealth.

Subsequently, the phrase "formation of socio-economic institutions of lifelong learning" positioned financial access as one of the components of ensuring the sovereignty of individuals. In conjunction with the understanding of finance as a system of social relations among many entities, which are formed not only in the financial services market, but also at the level of individual behavior and culture, it becomes obvious that it is not only the implementation of the functions of the state, but also the result of a combination of factors that influence the formation of financial valuations of individuals and their actual financial behavior [2].

Economic education helps people to approach financial issues consciously, achieve financial stability and overall well-being. At the same time, they make a significant contribution to the country's economy and the sustainable development of the global economic system.

Therefore, many different parties are interested in raising people's financial education: the state, banks, business, and citizens themselves.

The effect of teaching the population the basics of financial knowledge:

- the financial well-being of people shows augmentation due to the rationalization of the family budget, an increase in the planning horizon, and the development of the ability to manage finances during the family life cycle.

- people manage their debt obligations more efficiently, which include loans and credits.

- the population pays off debts in good faith and on time, which follows from the previous point. As a result, the credit reputation of the bank increases;

- the number of new loans issued to pay off old debts decreases, the number of non-repaid loans decreases;

- since the population is familiar with the mechanism of the banking system, the level of trust in banking services increases [3].

The topic of financial literacy has been drawing academic and practical interest given its potential impact on the economic development of a country. However, as experience shows, devoting separate attention to financial market participants in general and individuals, in particular, is vitally important. The basic guideline of the Knowledge-Based Economy concept that increasing the human capital stock contributes to economic development might be useful for choosing a line of development and application of the human capital category. It is generally

believed that financial literacy, closely associated with financial innovations, non-traditional financial products, and services, is regarded as a human capital component.

Belarus is not an exception in terms of financial market development issues. After the disintegration of the USSR, the Belarusian financial sector has been transforming from an ex-Soviet centralized economic system and, due to that, it represents an aggregate of traditional sectors, services, a limited quantity, and a set of operations, products, and services. The closure and expansion of financial market sectors have influenced the labor market, which has absorbed the majority of the enterprises and organizations' released workers, as well as students graduating from schools, colleges, and universities. Every citizen of Belarusian, being regarded as a permanent employee in general, makes payments into the state and non-budgetary social funds, making pension insurance premiums, as well as obtaining state and commercial loans, depositing savings, and making money transfers.

Currently, in the Republic of Belarus, work is underway to improve the financial literacy of the population in various directions. For example, the Center for Banking Technologies has developed a Single Financial Literacy Portal.

Technology and innovation go hand-in-hand with exploration new innovations for implementing SDGs acceleration in Belarus. Building the foundation for innovation involves professional training and experimenting with new forms taking into account the behavioral insights. As a result, the unified Internet portal of financial literacy was created by the National Bank of the Republic of Belarus. Its main goal is to help citizens improve their competencies in the financial sector. Basic financial information is presented in a simple and interesting way and will be useful when making financial decisions. Teachers, volunteers and other participants involved in this work can find information and methodological support here. On the official website, it is proposed to take tests to determine the level of financial literacy, games on various topics are provided, theoretical articles are located to increase the level of knowledge. The platform also creates and enables future-oriented opportunities for adolescents and youth to fulfil their labour potential and to remain to live and work in Belarus. This includes greater investment in improved vocational, educational and technical training programs. Such specific policies aim at strengthening the labour market institutions for young job seekers in order to support smooth school-to work transition and decent work conditions for younger less-experienced generations.

Over the 6 years of the Joint Action Plan to improve financial literacy of the population for 2019–2024, the number of citizens interested in improving their knowledge in the field of finance has increased significantly. Thus, in 2024, 71.9% of the surveyed participants used a savings policy, which is 15.7 percentage points more than in 2020. However, most people still resort to the "residual savings" strategy (more than 40%). At the same time, the population plans their finances for short periods of time from 1 to 3 months. Only 26.7% adheres to an effective spending strategy.

At the same time, there is a contradiction between the respondents' answers: 81.8% of people believe that a person with any income level needs to control their financial resources, but only 12.7% of respondents actually monitor their finances. Also, half of the respondents personally encountered fraud, 45% know about this phenomenon by hearsay and 2.5% suffered from fraudsters, losing money or personal data. About 70% of the surveyed population are motivated to study aspects of financial literacy. The value of the integrated index of financial literacy of the population increased compared to 2020 by 3.3 percentage points and amounted to 43.2% [4].

Thus, effective and productive government policies enable manufacturing sector, financial services and private business sector to flourish achieving overall state efficiency. It is clear that there is still a long way to go to improve the financial literacy of the population. Belstat is also planning to introduce some surveys in SDGs implementation related to finance management to track progress until 2030 [5].

Globally, the importance of financial literacy is vast. The financial crisis was a stark reminder of just how important financial markets, financial institutions, and financial products are for the overall health of global economies. The rise of non-bank services offers a rich set of new opportunities for countries as they move forward and seek to boost financial inclusion. Simultaneously, it presents a set of challenges for making sure that relevant laws are in place, are easily understood, and offer effective protection. Financial literacy is a key tool in addressing the challenges and maximizing the potential benefits from the rapidly changing landscape of financial services. Literate consumers become empowered consumers; it is a consumer that stands to benefit from the vast changes that are taking place in the markets for financial services.

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